

Cost-efficient Joint Network and Compute Resource Allocation in 6G Healthcare 4.0 Networks

U. Das^{*,†}, A. Mesodiakaki^{*,†}, C. Bratsoudis^{*,†}, and A. Miliou^{*,†}

^{*}Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece.

[†]Center for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation, Thessaloniki, Greece.

Abstract—Healthcare 4.0 (H4.0) applications such as telehealth and Internet of Medical things (IoMT) demand ultra-high capacity, low latency, extensive coverage, energy efficiency, and massive connectivity, stressing the limits of traditional Terrestrial Networks (TNs) infrastructure. The lack of ubiquitous terrestrial coverage and X-haul capacity bottlenecks necessitate integrated Terrestrial and Non-Terrestrial 6G Networks (TN-NTNs). However, high deployment cost and energy limitations of NTN demand efficient solutions to ensure scalable and sustainable healthcare delivery. This paper focuses on minimizing the Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) of the integrated 6G TN-NTN formulated as a joint offline cost-aware user association, traffic routing and Virtual Network Function (VNF) placement problem. A cost-efficient low complexity heuristic algorithm (named CHEUR) is developed and evaluated via simulations. The proposed solution is shown to significantly outperform the State-of-Art (SoA) in terms of energy and cost-efficiency, with CHEUR achieving up to 1.64 times higher energy efficiency and 73.85% TCO reduction. The problem is introduced within a H4.0 scenario which includes healthcare focused service function chains (SFCs) aligned with the latest ITU-R framework for IMT-2030.

Index Terms—Cost efficiency, energy efficiency, green networks, healthcare, service function chain (SFC), virtual network function (VNF).

I. INTRODUCTION

As mobile access networks evolve into denser configurations (from 1G to 6G), they face challenges related to interference management, network design, and efficient resource utilization. The rise of mission-critical applications in H4.0 [1] which involves healthcare’s digital transformation via real-time data, automation, and connectivity has increased the need for low-latency, reliable, and scalable communication for global coverage. Services like remote diagnostics and telemedicine demand uninterrupted quality of service (QoS), even in remote areas. The IMT-2030 framework [2] outlines six usage scenarios, including 5G enhancements (e.g., Immersive, Massive, and Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication) and new 6G paradigms (e.g., AI, Integrated Communication and Sensing and Ubiquitous Connectivity). Although these highlight the need for adaptive, cost-efficient infrastructure, high deployment costs remain a barrier to global H4.0 adoption.

These stringent requirements have catalyzed the evolution toward TN-NTNs architecture [3], which includes conventional ground infrastructure with aerial and satellite-based communication platforms. Despite their potential, Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs) comprising Low Altitude Platforms (LAPS), High Altitude Platforms (HAPS), and satellites,

face strict Size, Weight, Power, and Cost (SWaP-C) constraints that limit payload capacity, energy autonomy, and communication range, particularly as platforms transition from large GEO satellites to more compact LEO satellites and HAPs, requiring significant adaptation of high-frequency radio frequency (RF) and computing payloads.

A promising solution to this lies in the joint operation, which enhances network flexibility, effectiveness, and resource efficiency. This approach integrates access and X-haul, i.e., front-/mid-/back-haul, enabling resource pooling, interdependence, and improved cooperation for more efficient network management. Furthermore, using wireless backhaul (BH) links operating at Millimeter Wave (mmWave) frequencies can reduce BH deployment costs while providing multi-gigabit BH capacity [4].

To address the challenge of operating in a dense highly heterogeneous network, which may induce high power and operational cost (OPEX), Network Function Virtualization (NFV) has emerged as a key enabler, allowing service providers to reduce both OPEX and capital expenditure (CAPEX) by replacing traditional hardware-based network functions (e.g., Network Address Translation (NAT), Firewall (FW), Traffic Monitor (TM)) with software-based Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) that can be deployed on commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) servers [5]. This shift improves service flexibility and simplifies network management. However, efficiently placing these VNFs and orchestrating Service Function Chains (SFCs) across the *system-of-systems* architecture inherent in 6G networks remains a complex task as service reliability, TCO, and energy consumption need to be carefully balanced.

Enhancing energy efficiency and costs are crucial when considering the complete network path from the traffic source to the User Equipment (UE) to meet service latency requirements and achieve true end-to-end (E2E) efficiency within the operator’s network [6], while guaranteeing ultra-reliable and ubiquitous service delivery which are central to next-generation healthcare networks. Minimizing both OPEX and CAPEX is critical for sustainable network deployments, ensuring long-term economic viability. Additionally, optimizing costs and energy contributes to minimizing the environmental impact of Information and Communications Technology (ICT) sector, paving the way for eco-friendly and economically viable Beyond 6th Generation (B6G) H4.0.

A. Related Work and Contribution

Prior research has extensively explored individual aspects of user association (UA), resource allocation (RA), and VNF placement. In TNs, [7] addresses joint VNF placement and RA, while [8] focuses on UA and RA. Studies such as [6], [9], [10] extend these aspects to TN-NTN architectures. Joint access-BH solutions in [11] address integrated RA and UA but exclude aerial and space nodes. Studies like [6], [10] consider UA, routing, and VNF placement with a focus on energy efficiency. While this can lower OPEX, it does not guarantee overall cost reduction in deployments, where CAPEX for infrastructure and equipment is also critical, hence, overlooking the cost-energy efficiency trade-off in integrated 6G TN-NTNs. Although cost-aware VNF placement is explored in [12] and [13], and metaheuristic-driven VNF scheduling approaches are presented in [14], these works are largely limited to cloud or multi-access edge computing (MEC) infrastructures [15] [16], lacking consideration for non-terrestrial constraints, which are central to 6G's mission-critical and globally accessible service delivery.

While previous work has addressed UA, RA, and VNF placement individually or jointly, it overlooks the stringent demands of H4.0, which require high data rates, ultra-low latency, and massive connectivity to be met simultaneously. This work bridges that gap by jointly optimizing these key aspects in a healthcare-specific scenario within an integrated 6G TN-NTN based architecture, consisting of terrestrial, aerial, and space nodes at all orbits. To that end, energy-efficient, reliable, and cost-effective delivery of critical medical services is enabled through a cost-aware UA, routing and VNF placement approach that considers resource availability, path feasibility, delay, and cost efficiency.

Instead of solving an optimization problem, our framework greedily places VNFs on computational nodes and selects feasible routing paths based on latency compliance and minimal TCO. The TCO metric, comprising CAPEX (e.g., equipment, deployment) and OPEX (e.g., energy, operational costs), serves as the main criterion for infrastructure efficiency. Mobile network operators can use our proposed algorithm as an offline tool during network planning to deliver quantitative insights into cost, power consumptions and computational resources, which are the key contributors to OPEX and CAPEX for supporting specific services. We compare our method against a widely adopted SoA baseline [17], which allocates VNFs to nodes using betweenness centrality(BC) and shortest-delay method for routing without taking cost into account.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section II introduces the system model and the studied problem; Section III details the proposed cost-aware algorithm; Section IV presents simulation results and compares it to the SoA; Section V concludes the paper and presents our future work.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND STUDIED PROBLEM

We extend the model in [6] by incorporating cost considerations, explicitly accounting for CAPEX (based on infrastructure deployment) and OPEX (based on resource utilization).

Fig. 1: System model.

We consider a heterogeneous multi-tier mobile network comprising radio access (RAN) and core segments, represented by a directed graph $\mathcal{G}(\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$, where \mathcal{V} denotes the set of nodes and \mathcal{E} the set of directed links, as shown in Fig. 1. The node set \mathcal{V} includes terrestrial: gNodeBs (gNBs), small cells (SCs), aerial: LAPS, HAPS and space nodes (LEOs), which are called base stations (BSs) in RAN, and in core there are switches and computational nodes. Each node may provide radio access and/or computing capabilities and may host one or more VNF instances. Each node $y \in \mathcal{V}$ incurs OPEX $C_{\text{OPEX},y}$ and a one-time CAPEX $C_{\text{CAPEX},y}$. Each link $e = (u, v) \in \mathcal{E}$ interconnects nodes $u, v \in \mathcal{V}$ and may represent a wired (e.g., fiber) or wireless (e.g., mmWave, Free-Space Optical (FSO), Inter-Satellite Link (ISL)) medium. Each link is characterized by its capacity c_e (Mbps), latency δ_e (ms), and cost $C_e = C_{\text{CAPEX},e} + C_{\text{OPEX},e}$, where $C_{\text{CAPEX},e}$ is the one-time cost to deploy link e , and $C_{\text{OPEX},e}$ captures the usage-dependent operating cost. The set \mathcal{E} is partitioned into wired links \mathcal{E}_{fi} and wireless links \mathcal{E}_{wl} .

UEs are represented by the set \mathcal{J} , disjoint from \mathcal{V} . We define the extended node set $\tilde{\mathcal{V}} \triangleq \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{J}$. Each UE $j \in \mathcal{J}$ associates with a candidate access set $A(j) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$ based on signal-level criteria. A BS $a \in A$ is provisioned with $N_a^{(\text{RB})}$ Resource Blocks (RBs), allocated to UEs in its coverage area $S(a) = \{j \mid a \in A(j)\}$. Nodes capable of hosting VNFs form the subset $\mathcal{V}_c \subseteq \mathcal{V}$, where each compute node $y \in \mathcal{V}_c$ offers c_y GFLOPS and incurs CAPEX and OPEX. VNFs are drawn from the set \mathcal{F} , with each $f \in \mathcal{F}$ defined by the tuple $(T_f, \pi_f, w_f, \tau_f)$, representing VNF id, CPU demand (GFLOPS), per-Mbps processing load, and processing delay (ms) respectively. Each SFC $\rho \in \mathcal{C}$ is an ordered sequence $\rho = \langle f_1^{(\rho)}, \dots, f_{N_\rho}^{(\rho)} \rangle$, where traffic must traverse VNFs in

order. We write $f \rightsquigarrow \rho$ to denote that VNF f belongs to ρ , and define $\mathcal{R}_\rho = \{f \in \mathcal{F} \mid f \rightsquigarrow \rho\}$. Each UE $j \in \mathcal{J}$ requests a service $q_j = (s_{q_j}, r_{q_j}, \delta_{q_j}, \rho_{q_j}) \in \mathcal{Q}$, where $s_{q_j} \in \mathcal{V}$ is the service source, r_{q_j} is the data rate (Mbps), δ_{q_j} the delay budget (ms), and $\rho_{q_j} \in \mathcal{C}$ the required SFC. VNFs may be shared across UEs if the total demand remains within host capacity. For each UE j , the number of RBs $N_{a,j}^{(\text{RB})}$ on access link $(a, j) \in \mathcal{E}$ is computed from the estimated SINR $\sigma_{a,j}$ and the requested rate r_{q_j} . We define binary variables $x_{j,a}$ for UE-BS association, $\phi_{y,f,q}$ for VNF placement, and $\theta_{(u,v)}^{e',q} \in \{0,1\}$ to indicate whether physical link $(u, v) \in \mathcal{E}$ is used to route virtual edge $e' \in \mathcal{E}(\rho_q)$ in SFC ρ_q .

A. Problem Statement

We formulate the following problem:

$$\underset{x, \phi, \theta}{\text{argmin}} \text{TCO}, \quad \text{s.t. (4)–(10)} \quad (1)$$

where TCO is expressed as

$$\text{TCO} = \sum_{z \in X_{\text{deployed}}} (C_{\text{CAPEX},z} + C_{\text{OPEX},z}) \quad (2)$$

and the annual OPEX for each deployed element z being

$$C_{\text{OPEX},z} = (P_z \cdot g + C_{\text{maint},z}) \cdot H \quad (3)$$

X_{deployed} denotes the set of all deployed infrastructure elements, i.e., $X_{\text{deployed}} = A_{\text{deployed}} \cup \mathcal{V}_{c,\text{deployed}} \cup \mathcal{E}_{\text{deployed}}$ where, A_{deployed} is the deployed nodes (e.g., gNBs, SCs, LAPS, HAPS), $\mathcal{V}_{c,\text{deployed}}$ is the deployed computational nodes, $\mathcal{E}_{\text{deployed}}$ is the deployed communication links (e.g., fiber, mmWave); $C_{\text{CAPEX},z}$ is the one-time deployment cost of element z . From Eq. (3), $C_{\text{OPEX},z}$ is the annual OPEX for element z , P_z is the power consumption of element z in kilowatts (kW), where power models for each node or link type is shown in [6], [10], g is the electricity price in euros per kilowatt-hour (€/kWh), $C_{\text{maint},z}$ is the hourly maintenance cost for compute node z , H is the number of hours in a year (used to annualize energy and maintenance costs).

Eq. (1) is subject to the following constraints:

$$\sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}(j)} x_{j,a} = 1, \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{J} \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{y \in \mathcal{V}_c} \phi_{y,f,q} = 1, \quad \forall q \in \mathcal{Q}, \forall f \in \mathcal{R} \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \sum_{q \in \mathcal{Q}} \phi_{y,f,q_j} r_{q_j} N_{f,y} \pi_f \leq c_y, \quad \forall y \in \mathcal{V}_c \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{q \in \mathcal{Q}} \sum_{e' \in \mathcal{E}(\rho_q)} \theta_{(u,v)}^{e',q} r_{q_j} \leq c_e, \quad \forall e \in \mathcal{E} \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{S}(a)} N_{a,j}^{(\text{RB})} \leq \bar{N}_a^{(\text{RB})}, \quad \forall a \in \mathcal{A} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{v:(u,v) \in \tilde{\mathcal{E}}} \theta_{(u,v)}^{e',q} - \sum_{w:(w,u) \in \tilde{\mathcal{E}}} \theta_{(w,u)}^{e',q} \\ &= \phi_{u,h(e'),q} - \phi_{u,t(e'),q'}, \quad \forall q \in \mathcal{Q}, e' \in \mathcal{E}(\rho_q), u \in \tilde{\mathcal{V}} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{y \in \mathcal{V}_c, f \in \mathcal{R}_{q_j}} \phi_{y,f,q_j} \tau_f + \sum_{e \in \mathcal{E}, e' \in \mathcal{E}(\rho_{q_j})} \theta_{e'}^{e',q_j} \delta_e \\ &+ \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}(j)} x_{j,a} \delta_{(a,j)} \leq \delta_{q_j}, \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{J} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Constraints (4)–(5) ensure user acceptance, unique BS association, and proper VNF deployment. Constraint (6) ensures VNF processing demands do not exceed node CPU resources. Constraints (7)–(8) enforce link capacity and BS RB limitations. Constraint (9) ensures correct flow conservation along feasible paths that follow the SFC order, while (10) ensures end-to-end delay compliance. Due to the problem being NP-hard, we propose below a heuristic algorithm.

III. PROPOSED SOLUTION (CHEUR)

An offline cost-aware heuristic, named CHEUR, is proposed that jointly performs UA, traffic routing, and VNF placement to minimize network cost and improve energy efficiency while satisfying all UE requests. As shown in Fig. 2, CHEUR consists of two steps: UA and routing, followed by VNF placement in the SFC-defined order.

Fig. 2: Flowchart of Proposed Offline Heuristic for Cost-Efficient User Association, Traffic Routing and VNF Placement (CHEUR).

To enhance the UE acceptance rate, UEs are ordered according to their RB requirements, prioritizing resource-critical users over others, thereby improving system efficiency and fairness. For each UE, CHEUR builds a weighted graph incorporating all feasible paths from the SFC source to the UE (destination). The link weights reflect total cost, combining both CAPEX and OPEX (for X-haul and access links), while also considering resource sharing from users already processed by allowing reuse of already deployed VNFs and links, which contributes to improved cost efficiency.

The algorithm then calculates the k shortest paths in terms of cost and selects the one with the lowest overall cost (taking into account the decisions for the already examined UEs) that satisfies both the delay and capacity constraints. If the current path violates any constraint, the next-best path is considered. If no valid path exists, the UE is marked as blocked, and CHEUR proceeds with the next as long as there is one.

Once a path satisfying all constraints is found for the current UE, CHEUR proceeds to the second step, which is the VNF placement. For each VNF in the order specified by the UE's SFC, a list is constructed with all the available computational nodes. This includes the closeness node centrality, computational cost and the operational expenditure, which is the total additional cost incurred by placing the VNF on that node. CHEUR computes the TCO for each computational node along the currently selected path. TCO is defined as the sum of the additional CAPEX (which depends on the cost per GFLOPS used, based on the node's type and number of cores) and the additional OPEX incurred if a new instance is deployed. This cost component considers three cases:

- If the studied VNF can be hosted in an already deployed node without initiating a new VNF instance and without exceeding its processing capacity, the additional cost is zero.
- If the node is already deployed but requires a new instance, the additional cost includes only the corresponding OPEX.
- If the node is not yet deployed and a new instance must be initiated, then the corresponding additional CAPEX and OPEX are calculated.

The node with the minimum TCO and favorable centrality is selected to host the VNF, provided it has sufficient computational resources available. If no suitable node is found along the current path, the algorithm backtracks and evaluates the next path in the k shortest-cost list. This process is repeated until all VNFs in the user's SFC are placed or all paths are exhausted. If all VNFs are successfully placed, the network state is updated accordingly, and the algorithm proceeds with the next UE. This continues until all UEs have been processed.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

A. Scenario

We assess the performance of our proposed cost-efficient heuristic (CHEUR) algorithm against SoA benchmark from [17] through simulations in MATLAB R2024b. For each fixed number of UEs, we simulate 10 distinct scenarios. The network topology includes a macrocell with a central gNB in Thessaloniki, Greece [10], covering a 500-meter radius. Two SC clusters, each with four SCs uniformly placed within a 100-meter radius, are overlaid. The gNB and one randomly selected SC per cluster are fiber-connected to a two-tier transport network comprising fog and cloud layers, each with four fiber-connected nodes randomly chosen for full connectivity. mmWave X-haul links are assumed between BSs within 200 meters. Simulation parameters are summarized in Table I, for access and backhaul networks [10].

The satellite segment includes 1 Iridium, 15 OneWeb, 25 Starlink, and 2 GEO (Geostationary Earth Orbit) satellites

TABLE I: Simulation Parameters

Access Network	gNB	SC	LAPS	HAPS	LEO	
f [GHz]	2	2	28	28	28	
BW [GHz]	0.02	0.02	0.2	0.2	0.4	
N_{TRX}	128	32	64	64	128	
P_0 [W]	145	6.8	1	1	1	
Δp	4.2	4	2	2	1	
C_{CAPEX} [k€]	168	30	200	500	155	
C_{maint} [€/yr]	3360	1000	8369	10k	500k	
Backhaul Network	WTN	FTN	TN-NTN	A2S	A2A	ISL
f [GHz]	28	28	28	28	28	200000
BW [GHz]	0.2	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	20
N_{TRX}	32	32	32	64	64	128
P_0 [W]	3.9	3.9	3.9	3.9	3.9	3.9
Δp	5	1	4	4	4	10
C_{CAPEX} [k€]	33	40	37	200	155	2000
C_{maint} [k€/yr]	2	2	2	2	2	20

(HellasSat 3 and 4) with uninterrupted LoS, using orbital data from public ephemerides [18]. Terrestrial BSs are assigned 100 orthogonal RBs each, with inter-cluster frequency reuse among SCs potentially causing interference. Satellite and ISL links operate in high-frequency bands with minimal interference due to narrow-beam transmissions.

Fig. 3: Traffic pattern throughout the day with high and low traffic periods.

We consider a predefined hourly distribution of UEs per gNB sector over the course of a day, as illustrated in Fig. 3 which is based on the model from [19]. As outlined in Table II, the evaluation includes seven SFCs types, each defined by a sequence of VNFs such as NAT, FW, TM, WAN Optimization Controller (WOC), Intrusion Detection and Prevention System (IDPS) and Video Optimization Controller (VOC). Each SFC is defined by parameters including data rate range, latency bound, traffic share, service duration, and setup time. VNF processing requirements and CPU demands are based on values reported in previous studies [6].

B. Results

We present the simulation results in this section, comparing our proposed heuristic CHEUR with the SoA benchmark. Both approaches achieve 100% user acceptance across all time slots. Average TCO (EUR/year) is shown in Fig. 4, where CHEUR consistently outperforms the SoA across all traffic loads. The SoA incurs steep TCO increases from 6th hour, peaking between hours 8–12, while CHEUR maintains

TABLE II: Service Function Chain (SFC) Characteristics [6]

SFC Type	VNF Chain	Data Rate (Mbps)	Delay (ms)	Traffic Share (%)	Duration (s)	Setup Time (s)
Web Service	NAT-FW-TM-WOC-IDPS	[0.6-1]	500	20	120	15
VoIP	NAT-FW-TM-FW-NAT	[0.384-0.64]	100	10	100	10
Video Streaming	NAT-FW-TM-VOC-IDPS	[5-24]	100	30	360	20
Online Gaming	NAT-FW-VOC-WOC-IDPS	[0.24-0.5]	60	10	300	15
Ultra RT AI/ML	NAT-NAT	[15-25]	1	10	40	8
Telesurgery [20] [21]	NAT-FW-TM-WOC-NAT	[1-5]	170	10	6900	1320
Health Monitoring [22]	NAT-FW-TM-IDPS	[2-5]	50	10	540	40

significantly lower cost by deploying BSs and links with lower CAPEX and OPEX.

Fig. 4: Average TCO throughout the day (in €/year) for the proposed heuristic CHEUR and the SoA in logarithmic scale.

Fig. 5: Average number of deployed BSs for the proposed heuristic CHEUR and the SoA under low and high load.

Furthermore, Fig. 5 displays the average number of deployed BSs and Fig. 6 displays the average number of deployed BH, FB links, and compute nodes, for low (13 UEs) and high (235 UEs) demand scenarios respectively. From Fig. 5, it is observed that under low load, CHEUR deploys only two SCs, whereas SoA deploys a costly gNB, a SC and 2 LAPs. Under high load, CHEUR deploys seven SCs, and a LEO whereas SoA deploys one gNB, four SCs, and four LAPs, leading to higher TCO.

Moreover, from Fig. 6 it is apparent that compared to SoA, CHEUR deploys fewer BH links and compute nodes and deploys more fiber links, which is a cost effective choice.

Fig. 6: Average number of deployed computational nodes and links for CHEUR and the SoA under low and high load.

By prioritizing lower cost infrastructure such as SCs, which are more favourable than gNBs, LAPS, HAPS, and satellites (LEO), CHEUR reduces TCO by approximately 73.85% over the 24-hour profile (shown in Fig. 4).

Fig. 7: Average Energy Efficiency (EE) throughout the day (in bits/Joule) for the proposed heuristic CHEUR and the SoA in logarithmic scale.

Furthermore, Fig. 7 shows the average EE (in bits/Joule), which refers to the total data rate divided by the total power consumption and Fig. 8 shows the average execution time throughout the day. As traffic rises, during low demand hours (in Fig. 7), CHEUR exhibits a steeper and higher EE increase, peaking from the 6th hour onward. However, the SoA shows fluctuations in energy efficiency, as its static BC-based VNF placement and shortest-delay for routing overlook traffic and cost dynamics, resulting in suboptimal resource utilization and inconsistent performance under varying load conditions.

Fig. 8: Average execution time (s) throughout the day for the proposed heuristic CHEUR and the SoA in logarithmic scale.

CHEUR consistently outperforms the SoA, achieving on average a 1.64 times improvement in EE, at the expense of slightly higher execution time. This gain stems from CHEUR’s cost-aware strategy, which reduces energy by avoiding deployment of new nodes while satisfying the UE QoS requirements and selecting low-power backhaul routes. In contrast, the SoA relies solely on betweenness centrality and latency, often deploying unnecessary power hungry and costly nodes.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In order to enable H4.0 over integrated 6G TN-NTNs, we proposed CHEUR, a cost-efficient heuristic that jointly optimizes UA, routing, and VNF placement. By minimizing CAPEX and OPEX, CHEUR outperforms SoA in terms of energy- and cost-efficiency. Unlike traditional signal-strength or delay-based methods, CHEUR leverages cost-aware criteria to reduce both infrastructure and operational expenses, thus enabling truly sustainable 6G H4.0 systems. These benefits are achieved while maintaining relatively low complexity, particularly suitable for offline scenarios, as the ones studied in the paper, where execution time is less critical. Future work will introduce analytical benchmarks for further validation.

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